

ISic0756

I.Sicily inscription 0756

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Enna

Place of origin (modern)

Enna

Provenance

Contrada Li Perni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Enna, private collection

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493956

EDCS 35500003

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 186 no.70.1 fig.75

Li Gotti, A. 1955. Note su Philosophiana e Calloniana alla luce di nuovi rinvenimenti archeologici. *Archivio Storico Siciliano*. ser.III vol.7: 241-252. At 247

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